

Spatial Arithmetic and the Spatial Coefficient k

In this section, I will present the first steps toward a concept I call “Spatial Arithmetic”.

In Spatial Arithmetic, each number carries a subscript n that indicates the dimension of space it represents. When there is no subscript, the number exists in one dimension (a constant), representing magnitude or quantities defined on a one-dimensional scale.

Example: the equation $x^2 + 1 = 0$ has $x^2 = -1$.

If -1 has no subscript (i.e., one-dimensional), the equation has no solution.

If -1_2 (two-dimensional), the equation has a solution $x = -1$, which can be interpreted as the side length of a “hollow square” of length -1 . It means $(-1) \times (-1) = -1_2$.

Similarly: $(-1) \times (-2) = -2_2 \rightarrow$ the shorter side (-1) of a hollow rectangle multiplied by the longer side (-2) gives an area of -2 (a hollow rectangle).

If we compute $(-1) \times 1$ in one dimension, the operation simply tells us how many times (-1) is repeated: $(-1) \times 1 = -1$, or $(-1) \times 2 = -2$.

However, if (-1) and 1 belong to different spatial dimensions, the multiplication becomes meaningless—since the side of a hollow square cannot multiply by the side of a solid one. In such a case, the operation loses physical meaning.

Example: $x^2 = 1$

When 1 has no subscript (1D), the equation has $x = \pm 1$.

When 1_2 (2D), the equation has $x = 1$.

When 1_n (n-dimensional), we can rewrite:

$$x^2 = 1_n \Rightarrow (x^{2/n})^n = 1_n \Rightarrow x^{2/n} = 1 \Rightarrow x = \pm 1$$

At one dimension, arithmetic operations behave traditionally: for instance, $(-1) \times 2$ means “(-1) taken twice.”

But if -1 and 2 belong to different dimensions, the operation becomes invalid. In the Cartesian plane ($x = -1, y = 2$), multiplying $(-1) \times 2$ has no spatial meaning. A hollow side and a filled side cannot form a coherent object. Traditional arithmetic treats it symbolically as $(-1) \times 2 = (-2)$, but that is only a notation rule, not a spatial truth.

Or we can understand as: $-1_2 \times 2 = -2_2$ ie. a hollow square taken twice. Now, x let us know how many hollow squares, solid squares and y let us know how many times are made.

So, we can express: $-1_2 \times 2 = -2_2$ or $-1_2 \times -2 = 2_2$ or $1_2 \times -2 = -2_2$

But $-1_2 \times -1_1 = -1_3$ (compared with $-1_2 \times -1 = 1_2$), $-1_2 \times -2_1 = -2_3$ ($-1_2 \times -2 = 2_2$). This means the operation adds one more dimension.

Thus, when extending into higher-dimensional space:

$a_m \times b_n = c_{(m+n)}$ (when adding spatial dimensions, a, b, and c must share the same sign, with $|a| \times |b| = |c|$)

With this interpretation, we can apply root extraction, addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division to spatial numbers as an n-dimensional extension of traditional arithmetic.

This should not be confused with conventional arithmetic, where adding measurement units to coordinate axes is merely a matter of notation.

In Spatial Arithmetic, each number contains the spatial dimension within itself.

This is only a personal viewpoint that I would like to share from my own reflections. Thank you for reading these lines.